

CONFLICT AND MATERNAL MORTALITY IN BALOCHISTAN

Nadil Shah

PhD, Lecturer, Sociology University of Turbat

nadil.shah@uot.edu.pk

Corresponding Author: *
Nadil Shah

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16401118>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
19 April, 2025	23 April, 2025	08 July, 2025	24 July, 2025

ABSTRACT

War and health are correlated, and war creates abysmal health conditions because the provision of proper health facilities becomes very difficult in war-prone regions. In such situations, women and children are more affected than other segments of society are. In war situations, pregnant women often suffer because they need proper treatment and care, which they do not receive properly. Balochistan, a war-laden region, has also been treated like colonized by the Pakistani state rather than its federating unit. This inequality has led to very poor health conditions in Balochistan because of the conflict between Baloch separatists and the Pakistani government. In this study, researchers have attempted to understand the effects of war on health in general and maternal mortality, particularly in the province. In a 2019 report, the Maternal Mortality Survey of Pakistan revealed that the maternal mortality rate of Balochistan was 298 per 100,000 live births, which is higher than that of other federating units of Pakistan. Therefore, researchers have sought to understand the effects of war on increasing the rate of maternal mortality in Balochistan. This study was qualitative in nature and secondary data were through different sources such as research articles and books and newspapers. Those articles were selected which on war and health and maternal mortality especially focusing Balochistan. These qualitative data were analysed by using thematic analysis. The results of the study showed the there is significant relationship between conflict and maternal mortality. War effects the infrastructure such as roads, hospitals and other healthcare structures which directly or indirectly effect the increasing ratio of maternal mortality. Secondly, this study also showed that negligence of state also responsible for increasing the ratio of maternal mortal in Balochistan. The community as well as state despite conflict in Balochistan should provide maternal health services. Enough gynaecologists, paramedical states, emergency services and all necessary medicines should be provided at the hospitals in tehsil, district and divisional levels.

Keywords: Conflict, Maternal Mortality, Health, Balochistan, Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Balochistan, a province of Pakistan, borders Afghanistan, Iran, Sindh, and the Baloch Sea. Historically, Balochistan has split into three countries: Pakistan, Iran and Afghanistan (Breseeg, 2001; Inayatullah, 2009). Afghanistan, which includes Kandahar, Helmand and Nimruz,

occupies the smallest part. The Iranian part is known as Sistan-Balochistan. Pakistan has occupied the largest portion of Balochistan. Quetta is the provincial capital of Balochistan (Ali, & Panezai, 2021). The total population of Balochistan is 12.34 million according to the 2017

census of Pakistan. The greater population of Balochistan is Baloch (speak Balochi and Brahvi), whereas a small portion is composed of Pashtunes (speaking Pashto). Other minor communities, such as Hazaras, Uzbeks, Sindhis, Punjabis and Turkmens, also live in the province (Singh, 2020). The geographical area is 347,190 km long, which covers 43.6% (Erum, Saeed & Rehman, 2020) and occupies 1050 km of coastline (Siddiqui et al., 2008). Overall, Balochistan covers 60% of Pakistan, including land and sea areas. Balochistan is the richest and wealthiest province in terms of natural resources and geographical location, but it has deliberately kept most unprivileged, deprived and underdeveloped due to the lower interest of the federal government and incompetency and docile politicians of the province. Despite the 18th amendment in the constitution of 1973 in Pakistan, power was given to provincial units in 2010; the federal government decided the fate of Balochistan. The political leaders of Balochistan seem vulnerable and docile (Ozair & Khan, 2017, Ashraf & Shahzad, 2020). Hence, the political instability, injustice and unequal treatment of Balochistan by the federation has worsened the socioeconomic status of the people of Balochistan.

In terms of socioeconomic indicators, for example, the literacy rate of Balochistan is 54%, among which the female literacy rate is 44% (Qayyum, 2023). Similarly, Balochistan has the lowest human development index, which stands at 0.463 compared with other provinces and regions of the country (Waheed & Yousuf, 2022). Socioeconomic and sociodemographic characteristics are deteriorating conditions. Approximately 63% of people live below the poverty line, 75% of the population does not have access to electricity, 85% of residents do not have clean drinking water, and 70% of the population does not have access to basic education (Global Watch, 2023). According to the PPHI (People's Primary Healthcare Initiative) report (2020), there are a total of 8482 healthcare facilities throughout Balochistan, and the majority of the population lacks quality health in the province. The people of Balochistan make the federal and provincial governments responsible for such abysmal conditions, whereas the government of Pakistan,

coupled with the provincial government, claims that the ongoing freedom movement is responsible for such a distribution of social and economic structure.

Methods and Materials

Research Design

The nature of the study was qualitative because the collected data were qualitative and secondary sources. This study design helps the researcher to explanation and exploration of complex phenomena.¹ The qualitative study helped the researcher to understand the conflict and maternal mortality by focusing various narratives and socio-political arenas.

Data collection

For this study, data were collected through secondary sources such as newspapers, research articles and books. The collected articles were selected by using various inclusion and exclusion process. All those articles were selected which could fulfill the purpose of the study.

Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed by using thematic analysis. After collecting the data, latent thematic analysis was used. The themes were developed according to the data collected. Themes related to infrastructural issues and maternal mortality were developed as well.

Results and Discussion

Defining Maternal Mortality

Maternal mortality is the death of a mother during pregnancy or within 42 days of childbirth. The World Health Organization, a leading international organization working on health, has defined health in a global context. According to the WHO, maternal mortality is the death of a woman while pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of the duration and site of the pregnancy, from any cause related to or aggravated by the pregnancy or its management but not from accidental or incidental causes (World Health Organization, 2023). The maternal mortality ratio refers to the number of maternal deaths during a specific period per 100,000 live births (World Health Organization, 2021). The total population of women worldwide

is approximately 200 million; approximately 585,000 women die as a consequence of pregnancy or childbirth (Patwardhan, 2016). Maternal mortality is one of the leading causes of death in women worldwide. Thousands of women lose their precious lives during pregnancy or immediately after childbirth. It became an important issue in the health and gender discourse. The maternal health care that is provided, the selection of healthcare facilities for childbirth and other health facilities required for a pregnant woman show the value of women in society (Dahlen et al., 2022). On the other hand, all states of the world coupled with INGOs and NGOs have been working to prevent maternal deaths, but very few states have succeeded. Most developed countries have reduced the maternal mortality ratio to some extent, but this is still a great challenge for developing and developing nations. Millions of women die while giving birth to children, and the majority of them are in the least developed areas of the world.

Maternal Mortality in Pakistan

Pakistan, one of the least developed countries, has a high degree of maternal mortality. This is one of the greatest issues in Pakistan because its ratio is 186 per 100,000 live births despite spending \$225 million on foreign funded programs for improving maternal and child health in Pakistan (Rizvi, 2023). The ratio of maternal death also varies within Pakistan. For example, Punjab, the most privileged province, has the lowest ratio, and Balochistan, deprived of all facilities and developments, has the highest ratio of mothers' deaths (Bibi et al., 2023). Compared with that in previous years, the maternal mortality rate in Pakistan has decreased. In 2019, the maternal mortality ratio (MMR) was 186 deaths per 100,000 live births compared with 267 deaths per 100,000 live births from 2007-08. The report further highlighted that the maternal death ratio in rural areas is greater than that in urban areas in Pakistan. Approximately 199 deaths occurred in rural areas, while 158 deaths occurred in urban areas per 100,000 live births. The report also presented death cases on the basis of province. Among the provinces, Punjab has the lowest maternal mortality ratio, at 157; KPK, at 165; and

Sindh, at 224 per 100,000 live births. Kashmir and Gilgit-Baltistan have 104 and 157 deaths per 100,000 live births, respectively. Compared with other provinces of Pakistan, Balochistan has the highest maternal mortality ratio, which is 298 per 100,000 live births (National Institute of Population Studies, 2020). Many women die on a daily basis, even though most cases are unreported.

The causes of maternal mortality vary from place to place, but most of the causes highlighted by previous researchers are social, economic, structural/institutional, and clinical in Pakistan; however, they have focused less on war and maternal mortality, especially in the context of Balochistan. The government of Pakistan has dealt with Balochistan as a colonized rather than a unit. This colonizing and colonized relationship has divested the socioeconomic situation of Balochistan. In this article, researchers have attempted to understand the relationship between war and maternal mortality in Balochistan because war affects all aspects of the social life of people.

Maternal mortality in Balochistan: A situational analysis

The percentage of maternal mortality also varies according to region. The maternal mortality ratio is greater in rural areas than in urban areas in Pakistan. Compared with the other three provinces, Pakistan has the highest maternal mortality rate: Sindh, Punjab, and KPK. Dr. Rubaba Khan Buledi, Parliamentary Secretary Science and Technology, talking to a meeting of the WHO and Mother and Child Health (MCH), said that the ratio of mothers' deaths during childbirth is 298 per 100,000 per live birth, which is higher than that reported in 2019 and 2020 (Pakistan Observer, 2022). Various factors lead to maternal mortality, including political instability, medical complications, the unavailability of health facilities and the lack of recognition of danger signs for maternal mortality (Arif et al., 2022). Multiple factors, such as social, economic, and clinical factors, are involved in maternal mortality. Most women die due to social issues because they are treating second-class citizens. Many times, women are not taken to hospitals because of the unavailability of female doctors, and the treatment

of women by men is considered socially inappropriate. These cultural mindsets compelled women to give birth at home with the help of traditional attendees. Owing to gender discrimination, women are rarely taken to hospitals if the case is not very critical or serious. Likewise, antenatal care is very important, but women, especially those in rural areas, are deprived of this important opportunity. Rural women do not have agency. A lack of agency ability to make decisions independently is the leading cause of maternal mortality because the male member of the family makes the decision regarding her health. That man can be son, father, husband, or other influential community leaders. The power structure never supports women in being empowered and making decisions regarding health or other basic rights. Most importantly, religious rigidity is also involved in rural areas, as women are not taken to hospitals to give birth, as many women die at home. Instead of gender discrimination and social factors, economic inequality is a very important factor in maternal mortality.

Baloch Insurgency

It is the fifth wave of Baloch insurgency, which started in approximately 2000. Baloch insurgency is a social and political movement that started the alleged occupation of Balochistan by the Pakistani government in 1948 (Muzaffar, Karamat, & Saeed, 2018). When Pakistan separated from the subcontinent in 1947, Balochistan was in an independent state. Therefore, Pakistani politicians decided to merge Balochistan with Pakistan. Mr. Jinnah had visited Khan of Kalat and offered him for the merging Balochistan, but Khan of Kalat was not ready and replied Mr. Jinnah that he had to consult other Sardars, such as Sardars of Bela, Sarwan, Jalawan, Kharan and Makran. Despite waiting for a response, the Pakistani Army has allegedly occupied Kalat and jailed the khan of Kalat. Allegedly, the accession from Khan of Kalat and Balochistan was deliberately made part of Pakistan (Breeseg, 2001). Immediately after the alleged occupation, Baloch resistance started, and it is still ongoing. Owing to the war and conflict in Balochistan, all aspects of social life, including health, have been affected. Similarly, the situation

of maternal health in the province has deteriorated (Shah, 2024). As a result, the majority of mothers leave their precious lives because of maternal mortality, and war is directly or indirectly responsible for their deaths.

War and Maternal Mortality in Balochistan

Various studies have been conducted on social, medical and economic causes of maternal mortality, but few studies have been conducted in the context of war and maternal mortality, especially in Balochistan. War and maternal mortality are indirectly related, but little attention has been given to this topic.

War, Security Issues and Maternal Mortality

There are various causes of maternal mortality in Balochistan (Shah, Sultan & Siddiqui, 2023, Shah, 2024), but the political unrest in the region is also responsible for maternal mortality in Balochistan in general and in the Makran region, particularly because Makran is the most affected region in terms of political unrest. It is the fourth phase of Baloch insurgency, and the sociopolitical system of Balochistan has been completely disturbed (Aman, Akram & Saud, 2018). The insurgency of Balochistan also affects all social fabrics of society, including health. The government of Pakistan claims that effective and high-quality healthcare services cannot be provided due to political unrest in the region. The people of remotes are greatly affected because all basic necessities of living are not provided to them by the government for security reasons. Owing to the unavailability of basic necessities, qualified doctors and healthcare providers are not ready to provide services in remote areas. As a result, there is a very large gap in terms of access to health facilities. The government also claims that infrastructural development is not possible for security reasons. The lives of government contractors are in threat (Bashir et al., 2023). On the other hand, the people who are involved in insurgency believe that the state is looting our natural resources and that infrastructural developments are only for the sake of encountering the freedom movement (Prasand, & Patrick, 2023). This insurgency indirectly affects maternal health and mortality because of the

unavailability of healthcare providers and facilities for women, especially in remote areas of the region, pregnant women leave their previous lives. Political stability and peace ultimately help women receive timely healthcare facilities for their survival. The political conflict between the central government and the province affects the social, economic, educational, and political institutions of the provinces. These institutions ultimately affect healthcare institutions and services. Dysfunction of the health system directly affects the maternal and reproductive health of women in the region.

War, Infrastructural problems, and Maternal Mortality

War disasters destroy infrastructure and create hurdles for living people by affecting all the social, economic and health structures of society. Where there is war, there is no basic necessary infrastructure, such as hospitals, schools, roads or other basic structures. Similarly, Balochistan is a war zone, and infrastructure systems are in abysmal condition. For example, all remote areas are deprived of roads, schools, and hospitals and even high-level hospitals are built in such a way that every 5th vehicle meets an accident. The roads that connect Karachi to Quetta or Makran Coastal Highway, which connects Makran to Karachi, are the bloodiest roads (Bengali, 2018). It is a threat to the health of the local people of Balochistan, yet the government does not take serious action (Bashir, 2015). Because there are no proper roads and hospitals in remote areas are unavailable, many women leave their precious lives during delivery in Balochistan. The unavailability of proper and developed roads leads to delays in timely reaching hospitals in cities, resulting in delivery complications (Midhet, Becker, & Berendes, (1998)). Most mothers die on way to health facilities. If a person dies due to not reaching on time at the healthcare center, it is not the road; rather, it is the colonizing behavior of the government toward Balochistan. The colonized and colonized relationships have created hurdles in the health system of the province. Although the Pakistani government provides funds for the construction of roads and hospitals, the contractors never build effective and high-quality

infrastructures, and the state never makes them accountable for the misuse of funds and compromising structures. Accountability, maintaining quality, controlling corruption and ensuring the quality of infrastructures are the duties of the state, but they have never been serious. As a result, the MMR of the province has increased daily, and the health situation has worsened over time.

Despite roads, most mothers do not receive proper treatment within their villages or areas because of the unavailability of doctors and hospitals and healthcare services. For this reason, the government is responsible for their deaths because it is the responsibility of the state to provide them, but it is not possible in Balochistan because it is treated as colonized. For example, the government has provided funds for the construction of hospitals, but they do exist in reality or physically. Who did finalize? Who did audit and award the completion letter? If such a situation occurs, the state is directly or indirectly responsible for the unavailability of hospitals. If there are no hospitals nearby, emergency cases are taken to other areas, which takes time for the mothers to leave their precious lives.

Second, if the state has constructed buildings for hospitals and other services, such as doctors, medicines and emergency services are not available for maternal health, the state is also responsible for maternal mortality. For the UNDHR and SDG target 3.1, all states are responsible for proper health provisions and controlling maternal mortality to 70 per 100,000 live births annually. To prevent maternal mortality, the government of Pakistan has to provide all necessary health facilities to pregnant women in their native areas. If a pregnant woman receives all basic facilities on time, there is a high chance of maternal death. However, the government of Pakistan claims that Balochistan is in a war situation, owing to which it is impossible to provide health facilities. In real sense, the government has treated Balochistan as a colonized rather than its central unit. Most pregnant women are killed during operations in the villages of Balochistan. Therefore, it is not the unavailability of infrastructure; rather, it is the war and behavior of the Pakistani government that we are leaving the lives of mothers on a daily basis.

War, Healthcare Services and Maternal Mortality

Balochistan is deprived of all basic human necessities, such as electricity, gas, and proper networking systems. Similarly, healthcare services in Balochistan are completely unavailable, especially for pregnant women. There are some BHUs or health-providing centers in remote areas of Balochistan, but basic facilities such as medicines, gynecologists, and emergency ambulance services are lacking. Owing to the unavailability of healthcare services, all patients visit private clinics, which are operated mostly by men, who are medical technicians. Now, the question is why there are such facilities for the people. The answer would be colonization and war in the region. Balochistan is also treated as a stepchild by Islamabad because all natural resources, such as coal, gas, gold, and sea, are under the control of the federal government, and the people of Balochistan are deprived of the basic necessities of living. Therefore, people are concerned with the unequal treatment of the province. The majority of people believe that Balochistan has been occupied and looted by Pakistan since 1948. As a result, they started insurgency against the illegal occupation of Balochistan by Pakistan, and they believed in the freedom of Balochistan. On the other hand, the Pakistani government is trying very hard to counter insurgency by using different techniques. The Pakistani government and Baloch separatists are waging war against each other, and the Pakistani government has focused the least on health, especially maternal health. The maternal mortality rate is 298 per 100,000 live births, which reflects the alarming condition of child-mother health. Even though Sustainable Development Goal 3 ensures quality health provisions and reduces the maternal mortality ratio to 70 per 100,000 live births by 2030, it is impossible for the Pakistani government to achieve this target. There are many hospitals where there are no gynecologists or proper medicines by which patients are taken to cities through the help of private vehicles, which is time-consuming and expensive. As a result, many women live their previous lives due to preventable causes of maternal mortality.

War, Poverty and Maternal Mortality

A large population of Balochistan is living in absolute poverty because there are no job opportunities. The poverty rate of Balochistan is 71%, which is very critical. The government of Pakistan makes war responsible for poverty (Turk et al., 2023). On the other hand, Baloch believes that the government of Pakistan is exploiting its natural resources, and Baloch receives nothing in reward. Therefore, Baloch found war against exploitation. As a result, the poverty ratio is increasing each year. In poverty situations, receiving proper health facilities is impossible. Regardless of the situation, the country is responsible for providing good health to its people, but the state of Pakistan has failed to provide proper health to the people of Balochistan. Similarly, the majority of mothers die because they do not receive proper maternal health facilities because their families cannot afford. Poverty compelled families to delay emergency cases. They tried to obtain other sources first. For example, first, they try to obtain help from Dae/Dannabo (Tradition Health Attendant). Then, they visit medical technicians, mostly men, for 18 months. If they do not receive proper help, they try to arrange vehicles, which is usually not available. Because of the unavailability of facilities in the village, patients need to be taken to cities that are mostly 50 to 100 km long with dilapidated roads. These patients are taken to civil hospitals that do not have basic health facilities. Therefore, patient survival becomes impossible after such hurdles are faced. All these hurdles are due to poverty, and poverty is the result of colonization because colonizers never provide opportunities for colonization. Directly or indirectly, the war situation in Balochistan is responsible for maternal mortality, and it is the responsibility of the state to provide all facilities to its citizens despite war or any other uncertain situation.

Internal displacement persons (IDPs) and maternal mortality

In 2012, 149 million nondisplaced people were affected by arm conflict globally (13).

However, other causes, such as war and colonization, directly or indirectly contribute to maternal mortality in Balochistan. Maternal

mortality is alarming in Balochistan because its percentage is very high compared with that in other provinces of Pakistan. Most mothers lose their precious lives during or after childbirth, which is even preventable. It has been reported that it has broken the record of having one of the highest maternal mortality rates in the world (Shahid, 2020). Therefore, the present study concludes that war and colonization in Balochistan are responsible for the death of pregnant women. Importantly, the majority of the studies carried out have attempted to understand the causes of maternal mortality in the context of medical/biological causes while attempting to identify war and maternal mortality in Balochistan.

Conclusion

The present study was carried out to determine political unrest and maternal mortality in Balochistan. The findings of the study revealed that war affects health and mostly affects pregnant women because health facilities do not receive proper health facilities during war. The Pakistani government has treated Balochistan as colonized, and people have deliberately been deprived of all basic facilities. The political elites of Balochistan own all development funds, and they became war beneficiaries. They are also backed by the state and equally contribute to the exploitation and underdevelopment of Balochistan. On the other hand, Balochistan is in a state of war, and it is the fifth wave of insurgency, which is tactical and destructive for both sides. This situation affects all aspects of human life, but the health of pregnant women is affected the most. However, the war is not a justification for the state to not provide proper health facilities for its citizens; rather, the state must ensure the health of all citizens, especially pregnant women.

Author Contributions

N Sh conducted the study, collected data, wrote and edited the manuscript.

Funding

Author received no funds for this study.

Data Availability

The study data are available and will be provided upon request.

Competing Interest

Author declares no competing interests
Ethics, Consent to Participate, and Consent to Publish declarations are not applicable.

References

- Ali, A., & Panezai, S. (2021). Assessing the quality of primary health care services at basic health units in quetta city, balochistan, pakistan. *Public Health Res*, 11(1), 111-2.
- Aman, J., Akram, M. B., & Saud, M. (2018). Socio-Political Unrest in Pakistan: A Perception of University Students in the Province of Balochistan, Pakistan. *Matra Pembaruan: Jurnal Inovasi Kebijakan*, 2(2), 97-109.
- Arif, A., Sherani, A., Uzma, Q., Alam, B., Thom, E., Abro, A., ... & Baloch, F. (2022). Maternal and Perinatal Death Surveillance and Response in Balochistan, Pakistan-Causes & Contributory Factors of Maternal Deaths. *Journal of Gynecology and Obstetrics*, 10(1), 1-5.
- Ashraf, S., & Shahzad, A. (2020). Federalism and provincial autonomy in Pakistan: A case of Balochistan. *Pakistan Social Sciences Review*, 4(3), 25-35.
- Bashir, S., Khan, J., Danish, M., & Bashir, W. (2023). Governance and development challenges in Balochistan: A comparative study with other provinces and way forward. *International Journal of Contemporary Issues in Social Sciences*, 2(4), 620-649.
- Bengali, Q. (2018). *A Cry for Justice: Empirical Insights from Balochistan*. Oxford University Press.
- Bibi, S., Javed, S., Gul, M., Khan, R., & Bakhsh, F. M. (2023). A Seven Year Analysis of Maternal Mortality at Bolan Medical Complex Hospital, Quetta. *Journal of The Society of Obstetricians and Gynecologists of Pakistan*, 13(1), 23-26.

- Breseeq, T. M. (2001). *Baloch nationalism: Its origin and development up to 1980*. University of London, School of Oriental and African Studies (United Kingdom).
- Dahlen, H. G., Drandic, D., Shah, N., & Cadee, F. (2022). Supporting midwifery is the answer to the wicked problems in maternity care. *The Lancet Global Health*, 10(7), e951-e952.
- Erum, N., Saeed, N., & Rehman, T. U. (2020). Socioeconomic Development in Balochistan: A Dilemma. In *Civic Engagement in Social and Political Constructs* (pp. 26-43). IGI Global.
- Global Watch. (March 2023). *Pakistan in crisis, can Balochistan secede and decolonize*. Retrieved on June 23, 2023 from <https://www.firstpost.com/opinion/global-watch-with-pakistan-in-crisis-can-balochistan-secede-and-decolonise-12371772.html>
- Inayatullah, B. (2009). *The Problem of Greater Balochistan: A Study of Baloch Nationalism*. Cambridge University Press.
- Midhet, F., Becker, S., & Berendes, H. W. (1998). Contextual determinants of maternal mortality in rural Pakistan. *Social Science & Medicine*, 46(12), 1587-1598.
- Muzaffar, D. M., Karamat, S., & Saeed, K. (2018). Balochistan insurgency: causes and prospects. *Orient Research Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(1), 111-127.
- National Institute of Population Studies (2020). *Pakistan Maternal Mortality Survey 2019*. <https://nips.org.pk/publication/pakistan-maternal-mortality-survey-pmms-2019-main-report>
- Ozair, M., & Khan, J. (2017). The Content of the Eighteenth Constitutional Amendment and Balochistan: A Critical Appraisal. *Balochistan Review*, XXXVII (2).
- Prasand, H. & Patrick, W. S. (2023, January 24). Pakistan Faces Rising Separatist Insurgency in Balochistan. *New Lines Institute*. <https://newlinesinstitute.org/nonstate-actors/pakistan-faces-rising-separatist-insurgency-in-balochistan/>
- Pakistan Observer. (2022, October 19). 298 out of 100,000 die during childbirth in Balochistan. *Pakistan Observer*. <https://pakobserver.net/298-out-of-100000-die-during-childbirth-in-balochistan/>
- Patwardhan, M., Eckert, L. O., Spiegel, H., Pourmalek, F., Cutland, C., Kochhar, S., & Brighton Collaboration Maternal Death Working Group. (2016). maternal death: Case definition and guidelines for data collection, analysis, and presentation of immunization safety data. *Vaccine*, 34(49), 6077.
- PPHI. (2020). Annual Report- 2020. *PPHI Balochistan*. <https://pphib.org/pphib/publications/>
- Qayyum, F. (2023, March 24). Women's Education and its depletion in Balochistan. *South Asian Journal*. <https://southasiajournal.net/womens-education-and-its-depletion-in-balochistan/>
- Rizvi, I. (2023, December 25). Health expenditure and choices. *The DAWN*. <https://libraryguides.vu.edu.au/apa-referencing/7newspapers>
- Shah, N. (2024). *Causes of Maternal Mortality in Makran Divison, Balochistan*. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation). University of Karachi, Pakistan.
- Shah, N., Sultan, R., & Siddiqui, N. (2023). Social Determinants of Maternal Mortality: A qualitative study in Balochistan. *JOURNAL OF LAW, SOCIAL AND MANAGEMENT SCIENCES*, 2(2), 144-151.
- Shahid, S. (2020, Sept). Balochistan has the highest female mortality rate in the world. Retrieved on September 2, 2020. From <https://www.dawn.com/news/1578631/balochistan-has-highest-female-mortality-rate-in-the-world>
- Singh, H. (2020). Balochistan Province of Pakistan: Facts on its Geography and Economy. *Jagranjosh*. <https://www.jagranjosh.com/g>

- eneral-knowledge/balochistan-province-1567507454-1
- Siddiqui, P. J., Farooq, S., Shafique, S., & Farooqi, Z. (2008). Conservation and management of biodiversity in Pakistan through the establishment of marine protected areas. *Ocean & coastal management*, 51(5), 377-382.
- Turk, A. S., Hussain, R., Umer, Z., & e Ali, M. S. (2023). The Enigma of Balochistan's Socio-Economic Deprivation and The Way Forward. *iRASD Journal of Economics*, 5(2), 260-271.
- Waheed, A. K., & Yousuf, S. D. (September 2022). Human Development Disparities in Pakistan: Review of 2021 National Human Development Report. Retrieved on June 20, 2023, from <https://www.paradigmshift.com.pk/human-development-pakistan/>
- world health organization. (2021, june). herams balochistan baseline report 2021: operational status of the health system. <https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/herams-balochistan-baseline-report-2021-operational-status-of-the-health-system#:~:text=herams%20has%20been%20deployed%20in,estimate%20of%201661%20to%20date>
- world health organization. (2023). *trends in maternal mortality: 2000-2020: estimates from who, unicef, unfpa, world bank group and the united nations population division*. world health organization. retrieved on june 18, 2023 from <https://www.who.int/publications/item/9789240068759>

ⁱ Lee, Thomas. *Using qualitative methods in organizational research*. Sage, 1999.